

Original Research Report

Food Safety and Hygiene Practices of Hospitality Industries in Damaturu, Yobe State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study investigated food safety and hygiene of practices among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State, Nigeria. Its specific objectives were to ascertain food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State and determine barriers to food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State. The study design was descriptive cross sectional, which utilized a sample size of 180 from an estimated population of 285. Multistage sampling was used comprising random sampling, stratified sampling and proportionate sampling techniques. Instrument for data collection was questionnaire. The data were analyzed through descriptive statistics (frequency tables and percentages) and Chi-Square (χ^2). The findings of the study showed that the majority of the respondents were between the ages of 26-45 years old, female with either a secondary or a tertiary level of education, and operating in Damaturu LGA, which is an urban area, compared to Potiskum. It was already revealed that greater proportion of the respondents who engaged in practice of food safety and hygiene practice are slightly above 50%. However, lack of training and law enforcement were identified as major challenge to practice of food safety and hygiene. Furthermore, prior attendance of training on food safety and hygiene and LGA of resident had statistically significant influence on the practice of food safety and hygiene. Following the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that government and hospitality industries sector through its enforcement agency should make policies and regulations to make training on food safety and hygiene practice a necessity as it is an important to achieving better quality and improved food handling practices.

Keywords: Damaturu, Food Hygiene, Food Safety, Hospitality Industry, Training

1. Introduction

Food safety issues and hygiene practices have been a global concern, especially in the hospitality industry. Large populations of people are affected by foodborne and health-related complications annually (Klimpel, Kuhn, Münster, Dörge, Klapper & Kochmann, 2019). Globally, millions of people are predictable to have post-food consumption diseases such as food poisoning and Food Borne Diseases (FBDs). Adu-Ampong (2018) reported the global burden of food borne diseases to about 600 million with about 420, 000 deaths annually resulting in the loss of about 33 million Healthy Life Years (HLYs). This therefore has led to significant negative impact on the health status of the population and as such creates simultaneous enormous social burden on the society and the health system (Dzeagu-Kudjodji, Adjibolosoo & Otoo-Arthur, 2019). The greatest impact of foodborne diseases has been reported in Africa (Amoako et al., 2019). Akintaro (2012) reported that food poisoning and FBDs issues yearly had resulted to 33 million disabilities with a predictable cost of sickness placed at US\$3.6 billion in Nigeria yearly. This circumstance is attributable to inadequacy, out of order or poor food hygiene and safety practices among food handlers.

In Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa at large, despite the efforts of government through its National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), to improve the safety of food supply and practices, food safety still remains a major issue that has been worsened by the ignorance and poor food hygiene practices, uncoordinated approach to food safety control as well as poor enforcement of food safety policies and regulations (Omojokun, 2013). Similarly, climate change that result to temperature changes has been projected to influence the risks associated with food production, storage and distribution (WHO, 2015). This therefore has placed greater responsibility on food vendors such as hospitality industries to ensure utmost hygiene practice to ensure safety of food that they prepare for public consumption.

Food hygiene refers to or portrays conservation and grounding of foods in a way that ensures that the food is safe and protected for human consumption (Filimonau & Delysia, 2019). Food hygiene normally deals with the avoidance of food infectivity at all phases of production, collection, transportation, storage, preparation, sale and consumption. Diseases such as E.coli 0157:H7 contaminations linked to ground beef and ready-to-eat chicken salads, Listeriosis related with dairy yield, Salmonella infections associated to cucumbers, Hepatitis A connected to frozen berries, might occur when contaminated foods are consumed (Bintsis, 2017). The practices of food hygiene and food safety measure incorporate a variety of processes, which must to be complied to prevent the likelihood of harshly unsafe health conditions (Frazzoli, 2020). Such processes may include regular hand washing before and after handling food, covering of head and wearing of apron, as well as proper storage facilities. Food hygiene ensures maintaining hygienic and moderately germ-free setting. Hygiene issues in food process encompasses worth of raw food, individual and environmental hygiene as well as the facilities or materials that are involved in the food processing processes. WHO (2015) outlined some basic principles of food hygiene, they include prevention of food infectivity with pathogens, detach raw foods from cooked foods, cook food for suitable period and at the correct warmth, so as to kill pathogens and preserve the nutrients of the food, preserve food within required temperature and use of safe raw materials and water. Ndu and Asiegbu (2021) stated food hygiene as all circumstances and measures needed to ensure the safety and aptness of food at all phases in the food chain. This implies that utmost practice of food hygiene guarantees safety of food consumption and will not endanger the lives of the consumers. However, food hygiene requires regular practice to achieve food safety.

Practices refer to the ways in which individuals demonstrate their knowledge and attitude through their actions (Aiken et al., 2003). Hence, food safety practices can be regarded as activities and procedures involved in ensuring that food that is consumed does not cause harm but accomplishes its desired purpose (Lagerkvist, Amuakwa-Mensah & Tei Mensah, 2018). Food safety and hygiene are essential in promoting and preserving the health of the consumers, given that food borne diseases are significant contributors to morbidity and mortality globally (WHO, 2015). According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), unhygienic food has been implicated in the outbreak of several foods related illnesses with factors such as poor food handling practices of food vendors as the major culprit (FAO, 2022). The act of hand washing and other safety and hygiene practices are some suggested measures to halt the transmission of pathogens causing food borne diseases and significantly reducing the contamination of food. Curbing and minimizing the devastating effects of foodborne diseases, there is a need to ensure that food safety practices are effectively employed particularly in the hospitality industries.

Safety practices have become relevant in the hospitality industry globally, Nigeria inclusive due to the increasing interest in tourists and continuous demand for food outside their homes which is synonymous with modern lifestyle trends. Obviously, modern lifestyles have made it that most people, especially in the working class and urban dwellers alike, to depend on food and nourishment outside their home. Such person as a result depends on hospitality industry for breakfast, lunch, supper and even late-night snacks (Alagiyawanna, 2018). In the course of such dependency on food from outside their home, are therefore prone or vulnerable to incidences of food poisoning and other FBDs. This is because many persons manipulate large scale cooking such as that evident in the hospitality industry, food, which increases the plausibility of food contamination (Akabanda, Hlortsi & Owusu-Kwarteng, 2017).

Food contamination can occur at any point of production and distribution along the farm to plate continuum and as a result, food safety control is a responsibility shared by all components in the food supply chain; so, with each component operating responsibly, the supply of safe food to the consumer is supposed to be guaranteed. However, unfortunately, improperly prepared and mishandled food-by-food vendors and food handlers at home cause a large proportion of food borne diseases. One of the major challenges in food safety is that the food handlers lack understanding of their roles in ensuring proper personal and environmental hygiene as well as the basic food hygienic practices relating to buying, preparing and sell food (WHO, 2015). No doubt, unsafe food can affect the reputation and patronage in hospitality industries as it affects choice of eatery. There is therefore the need to examine food safety and hygiene practices of hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The consequence of improper or unhealthy hygiene practices of food handling has result to a great increase in food poisoning and Food Borne Diseases (FBDs) globally. According to World Health Organization (2015), the magnitude of FBDs caused by contaminated food and water significantly contributed to a myriad of health problems. Food handling personnel are assumed to be responsible for most illnesses resulting from poor handling behaviour. Angelillo, Viggiani, Rizzo, and Bianco (2000) argued that although food-handling personnel played an important role in producing food for consumption, they were likely to contaminate the food by introducing pathogens in the process of preparation, production, processing, distribution and service. Studies by Akonor and Akonor (2013) indicated food safety was a public health problem associated with consumption of food and water,

mainly triggered by improper food handling practices. Consequently, WHO (2015) reported that over 30% of persons in developed countries suffered illnesses related to consumption of food and water. This therefore indicates that food safety and hygiene practice are major global health challenge. This is also applicable in Nigeria and Damaturu, Yobe State in particular.

Rapid urbanisation, globalisation, increase in population as well as change of eating habits has led to a significant increase in the growth of the food service outlets and hospitality industries. This scenario is also obtainable in Damaturu, Yobe State. Because of this, individuals venture into hospitality industries and food management without good knowledge and the needed requirements for proper food safety management and hygiene practice. Despite the economic benefits in the sector, it viewed to posse serious danger and potential health hazards due to improper food handling and poor hygiene practices. There is therefore a critical need to ascertain food safety and hygiene practices of hospitality industries, particularly in Damaturu, Yobe State to ensure that FBDs caused by improper food handling practices are eradicated.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the food safety and hygiene practices of food handlers in the Damaturu Yobe State. Specifically, the study sought to:

- (a) Ascertain food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State.
- (b) Determine barriers to food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State.
- (c) Examine hygiene practices of food vendors among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What is the food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State?
- (b) What is the barrier to food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State?
- (c) What is the hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The study design was descriptive cross sectional, which utilized a sample size of 180. The minimum sample size was estimated using Cochran Cochran (1963) formula $n = z^2pq/d^2$. where n = minimum sample size required; Z = Standard normal deviate corresponding to the probability of type I error; p = proportion of food vendors estimated to have a certain safety and hygiene practice, which is set at 50%; $q = 1 - p$; d = tolerable error of margin set at 0.05. The sample size (n) calculated was 384. The population (N) of the food vendors in Damaturu was established to be 285, using the finite population correction factor (Roger, 2006). The adjusted sample size (n_0) = $n \times N/n + (N - 1)$. The adjusted sample size (n_0) for this study was 164 but was increased to 180 participants to accommodate non-response.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The faculty research ethics review committee gave its approval to the project. The proper distribution of study-related information, consent and assent forms was made. The author received permission from the secondary school institutions to perform the research. Additionally, the consent of the participants' parents was requested and authorized by the corresponding secondary school administrators. The attendees also expressed their agreement. The researcher also conformed with the ethical standards for research involving human subjects.

2.2. Area of the Study

The area of the study was Damaturu, Yobe State. Damaturu is one of the 17 LGAs in Yobe state. Its headquarters is in Damaturu town and consists of several towns and villages, which include Sasawa, Bayan Tasha, Gwange, Maisandari, Bindigari, and Lamisula. Damaturu LGA covers a total area of 2,366 square kilometres and has an average temperature of 35 degrees centigrade. It has an estimated population of 194,089 inhabitants. The LGA is predominantly urban and many hospitality industries and activities abound in the area hence, the necessity for the study in the area.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population (N) of the food vendors in Damaturu was established to be 285, using the finite population correction factor (Roger, 2006). The adjusted sample size (n_0) = $n \times N/n + (N - 1)$. The adjusted sample size (n_0) for this study was 164 but was increased to 180 participants to accommodate non-response.

A multistage sampling technique was used and this included the following stages: two local government area (Potiskum & Damaturu) were selected through a simple random sampling method. Secondly, a comprehensive list of existing catering establishments was obtained from the Department of Public/Occupational Health, Ministry of Health Damaturu, Yobe State. They were stratified according to the type of service they provide into the following strata: Restaurant 16, bar 8, butcher shop 12, juice vendor 9, totaling 45 food establishments. The main purpose of stratification was to avoid over or under-representation of certain types of establishments. A proportional sample size was used to determine each stratum, and selection performed using a table of random numbers to obtain a sample size of 180 from an estimated population size of 285. Four categories of food handlers were identified, which include Production staff, cooks, butchers, and waiters

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

Data was collected using questionnaires and checklist.

2.5. Data Analysis Technique

Data obtained were coded and analyzed with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Descriptive statistics (frequency tables and percentage) were generated. Chi Square (χ^2) was used to determine the relationship between characteristics of the respondents and practice of food safety and hygiene practices with the p value set at 0.05 significant level.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (%) n = 180
Age (years)	15 - 25	30(16.6)
	26 - 35	66(36.0)
	36 - 45	60(33.7)
	>46	25(13.7)
Sex	Female	125(69.4)
	Male	55(30.6)
Level of Educational	Primary	30(16.7)
	Secondary	60(33.3)
	Tertiary	70(38.9)
	None	20(11.1)
LGA of residence	Potiskum	66(36.7)
	Damaturu	114(63.3)
Duration of vending (years)	Below 5 years	65(36.1)
	5 and above	115(63.9)
Prior training in food safety	Attended	105(58.3)
	Not attended	75(41.7)

Data in Table 1 showed that majority of the respondents (69.5%) were between the ages of 26 and 45 years old with greater number of them being female (69.4%) and having either a secondary (33.3%) or tertiary (38.9%) school education. It also revealed that majority of the respondents (63.9%) have been in the business for over 5 years and operate within Damaturu (63.3). However, few of the respondent (41.7%) attended prior training on food safety.

3.1. Research question one: What is the food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State?

Table 2: Food Safety and Hygiene Practices

Food Safety and Hygiene Practices	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Proper hand washing with soap and water before and after handling food	Always	120	66.7
	Most of the time	45	25.0
	Sometimes	13	7.2
	Never	2	1.1
	Total	180	100.0
Sanitizing/disinfecting utensils before and after use	Always	105	58.3
	Most of the time	65	36.1
	Sometimes	8	4.4
	Never	2	1.1
	Total	180	100.0
Use of cooking apron and covering head	Always	83	46.1
	Most of the time	55	30.6
	Sometimes	40	22.2
	Never	2	1.1
	Total	180	100.0

Covering of wound and cuts when handling food	Always	74	41.0
	Most of the time	55	30.6
	Sometimes	46	25.6
	Never	5	2.8
	Total	180	100.0
Staying off work when sick	Yes	155	86.1
	No	25	13.9
	Total	180	100.0
Use of proper waste disposal methods	Always	108	60.0
	Most of the time	54	30.1
	Sometimes	16	8.9
	Never	2	1.1
	Total	180	100.0
Level of practice	Good	94	52.2
	Poor	86	47.8
	Total	180	100.0

Table 2 showed that majority of the respondents (66.7%) agreed that practice of washing hand always is necessary before and after handling food, however, 25%, 7% and 1.1% practice hand washing most times, sometimes and never respectively. Majority of the respondents affirmed the necessity for sanitizing utensils before and after use (58.3%) and use of cooking apron and head cover. In addition, majority of the respondents affirmed that they cover wound and cuts when handling food (41.0%) and stay off work when sick (86.1%) in order to lessen the possibility of compromising the safety of food. Greater number of the respondents (60.0%) affirmed that they always use proper waste disposal methods. Generally, 52.2% of respondents were found to engage in good practices of food safety and hygiene.

3.3. *Research question two:* What is the barrier to food safety and hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State?

Table 3: Barriers to Food Safety and Hygiene Practice

Variables	Male Freq.(%)	Female Freq.(%)	Total Freq.(%)
Lack of law enforcement	25(13.9)	15(8.3)	40(22.2)
Insufficient water supply	8(4.4)	6(3.3)	14(7.8)
Lack of time	11(6.1)	9(5.0)	20(11.1)
Lack of training	65(36.1)	38(21.1)	101(56.1)
Laziness	2(1.1)	1(0.6)	3(1.7)

Data in Table 3 showed respondents' opinion on barriers to food safety and hygiene. From the result, lack of training (56.1%) was identified as a major barrier to food safety practice, followed by lack of law enforcement (22.2%), lack of time (11.1%), and insufficient water supply (7.8%). Further, 1.7% of the respondents took the view that laziness is also a barrier to food safety.

3.2. Research question three: What is the hygiene practices of food vendors in Damaturu, Yobe State?

Table 4: Relationship between Characteristics of the Respondents and Food Safety and Hygiene Practices

Characteristics	Food Safety Practice			χ^2	p-value
	Good Freq.(%)	Poor Freq.(%)	Total		
Age					
<25	28(50.9)	27(49.1)	55(100)	0.512	0.474
>25	69(55.2)	56(44.8)	125(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
Sex					
Male	25(52.1)	23(47.9)	48(100)	0.022	0.884
Female	72(54.6)	60(45.5)	132(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
Level of education					
Primary	7(31.9)	25(78.1)	32(100)	1.490	0.222
Post Primary	90(60.8)	58(39.2)	148(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
Marital status					
Married	48(53.9)	41(46.1)	89(100)	0.002	0.893
Single	49(53.8)	42(46.2)	91(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
LGA of residence					
Damaturu	81(61.8)	50(38.2)	131(100)	5.152	0.023
Potiskum	7(17.5)	33(82.5)	40(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
Duration of vending					
Below 5 years	56(54.4)	47(45.6)	103(100)	0.113	0.737
5 years and above	41(53.2)	36(46.8)	77(100)		
Total	97	83	180		
Prior training on food safety					
Attended	65(70.7)	27(29.3)	92(100)	8.018	0.001
Not attended	32(36.4)	56(63.6)	88(100)		
Total	97	83	180		

Table 4 illustrated views of respondents on relationship between characteristics of the respondents and food safety and hygiene practices. The association between food safety and hygiene practice and the characteristics of the respondents such as age, sex, level of education, marital status, duration of food vending, attendance of training on food safety and LGA of resident and revealed that only prior attendance of training on food safety and hygiene and LGA of resident had statistically significant influence on the practice of food safety and hygiene. However, level of education was also found to have slight significant ($\chi^2 = 1.490$; $p = 0.222$) influence on food safety and hygiene practices of the respondents. The odds of good practice of food safety and hygiene among those who had previously attended at least a training was found to be higher (70.7%) than those who had not attended any training (36.4%) ($\chi^2 = 8.018$; $p = 0.001$). Also, the odds of good practice of food safety and hygiene among

food vendors who operate in Damaturu area was found to be higher (81%) than those operate in Potiskum area (17.5%) ($\chi^2 = 5.152$; $p = 0.023$).

This study investigated food safety and hygiene of practices among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State, Nigeria. The overall results showed that age, level of education and training were significantly associated with the level of food safety and hygiene practice of food vendors in the study area.

3.4.1. Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Respondents: The findings of the study showed that majority of the respondents were within the ages of 26-45 years old, female with either a secondary or tertiary level of education and operating in Damaturu LGA which is an urban area compared to Potiskum. The age of the respondents in this study revealed a relatively young group of food vendors which is in synergy with the studies of Odonkor and Odonkor (2020), Afolaranmi et al. (2013) and Iwu et al. (2017) in Ghana and Nigeria respectively. Majority of the respondents were also found to be females which can be attributed to the fact that cooking is believed to be a feminine business in a contemporary African and Nigerian setting. This validates the finding of Afolaranmi, Hassan, Bello and Misari (2015) who reported similarly findings. No doubt, the result is not surprising in a contemporary African setting as females have major responsibilities of preparing household food, hence food vending could be viewed as largely a female's business, however it does not mean that males are left out in food business. Majority of the food vendors had secondary school education and tertiary education and have attended prior training before venturing into the food vending. This corroborates the findings of Odonkor and Odonkor (2020), Al-Kandari, Al-abdeen and Sidhu (2019) and Afolaranmi et al. (2013) in Ghana, Kuwait and Nigeria respectively. Indeed, acquiring basic education and training are important in food vending business, as it requires basic ability to read and write to ensure conformance to basic food safety and hygiene requirements in some instances. The high number of the respondents having higher level of education may be attributed to the increasing lack of employment opportunities for the skilled and educated, thereby increasing the number of educated people engaging in self-employment activities like the food vending service as a source of livelihood. According to Afolaranmi et al. (2013), periodic training on the principles of food safety and hygiene is a key strategy to improving and promoting safe food handling practices. Years of experience of duration of time spent in food vending business maybe said to some extent but not unequivocally influence the practices of food safety and hygiene as it is in most businesses for which there are the tendency to improve in skills and competency with time. In this regard, the study found that majority of the respondents (63.9%) had spent 5 years or more in food business. However, this is in contrast to the findings of Madaki and Bavorova (2019) and Out (2014). The difference in the findings can be attributed to fact that majority who venture into the food vending business most times advance in it because of the profitable nature of the business.

3.4.2. Food Safety and Hygiene Practices: Proper food safety and hygiene practices is the normal standard or norm in any food and related facilities. Nevertheless, this standard most times appears wanting and as a result increase the risk of food contamination. This is obvious from the findings of this study where the greater proportion of the respondents who engaged in good practice of food safety and hygiene practice are at average or slightly above 50%. This is in corroboration with the findings of Odonkor and Odonkor (2020) and Aiken (2003) who reported similar findings but significantly higher than what was obtained in this study. However, findings of studies from Malaysia and other part of Nigeria reported better practice of food safety and hygiene (Nigusse, D. & Kumie, 2012; Iwu et al., 2017). The variation in these findings could be caused by the dissimilarity in the settings where these

studies were conducted as well as differences in food handling structures and facilities available in addition to prior attendance of training in this regard. The study found that majority of the respondents always practiced proper hand washing before and after preparing food. This is similar to the findings of studies carried out in Turkey and Nigeria but better than what was obtained elsewhere in Nigeria (Tuncer & Akoglu, 2020; Iwu et al., 2017). These findings could be attributed to the fact that access to water and the presence of hand washing facilities were inbuilt structures within most of the food vending premises.

3.4.3. Barriers to Food Safety and Hygiene Practice: Findings on opinions of the respondents regarding barriers to food safety and hygiene practice indicated lack of training, lack of laws enforcement, insufficient water supply and laziness as barriers to good practice of food safety in Damaturu among food vendors. However, this study identified lack of training as major barrier to food safety and hygiene practice. Regular training of food service personnel is highly needed to ensure improved food safety knowledge and practices (Alqurashi, Priyadarshini & Jaiswal, 2019). However, Nayak, R. & Waterson (2017) reported that barriers to food safety practice could vary in different regions, which could affect direction of policymaking and stakeholder decisions. In the light of this, organizations and institutions of practical programmes will be helpful to equip food vendors and handlers with best food safety practices in the hospitality industry.

3.4.4. Relationship between Characteristics of the Respondents and Food Safety and Hygiene Practices: Training indeed of any kind is essential when it comes to anything activity relating to human health. Prior attendance of training on food safety and hygiene as well as operating in urban area were significant determinants of practice of food safety and hygiene in this study. However, other factors such as training, operating in urban setting as well as increasing age of the respondents, level of education, sex, knowledge of food safety, marital status, income, availability of shower and separate dressing facility were reported in other similar studies (Abdullahi et al., 2016; Fasoro, Faeji, Oni & Oluwadare, 2016; Afolaranmi et al., 2015). Indeed, training plays an important role in the improvement of food safety and hygiene practice among food vendors. According to Monney, Agyei and Owusu (2013), training of food vendors is important in ensuring good personal and environmental hygiene. In the same vein, the authors reported that food vendors trained on food hygiene and safety are more likely to keep their finger nails clean and adequately protect their food from flies and dust.

4. Conclusion

This study examined food safety and hygiene of practices among hospitality industries in Damaturu, Yobe State, Nigeria. The findings showed that there is moderate level of practice of food safety and hygiene among the respondents. Therefore, food safety and hygiene practices require improvement as healthiness as well as utmost safety of food is vital to preservation and promotion of health. There, the government agencies saddled with the responsibilities of food related matter should ensure regular check on hospitality industries and food vending aspect in particular. In addition, the individual food vendors should as well brace up on hygiene practice such as washing of hand and utensils before and after use. Similarly, training was identified as a major factor for good practices and barrier to food safety. Therefore, government and hospitality industries sector through its enforcement agency should make policies that will make training on food safety and hygiene practice a necessity as it is an important to achieving better quality and improved food handling practices.

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum, Yobe State, Nigeria and also to the good people of Sasawa, Bayan Tasha, Gwange, Maisandari, Bindigari, and Lamisula for their support during the research work.

Conflict of Interest

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: RE.

Funding acquisition: RE,

Methodology: RE,

Data analysis: RE,

Writing – original draft, review & editing: RE.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Funding Information

The author has no funding to disclose.

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